

THE CRITERIA OF THE SPIRITUAL DEVELOPMENT OF YOUTH

D.A.Mutalov

State Conservatory of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
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Abstract. In this article, the youth who are the future of our country are to be educated spiritually, morally and physically, and to make them active participants in the ongoing reforms. special attention is paid to the problems of character education and development.

Keywords: Spirituality and enlightenment, culture, large-scale changes, State policy on youth, society, intellectual, era, thinker, universal.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Mamlakatimizning kelajagi bo'lmish yoshlarni ma'naviy-axloqiy va jismoniy barkamol etib tarbiyalash, ularni olib borilayotgan islohotlarning faol ishtirokchisiga aylantirish. Mamlakatimiz oldida turgan ijtimoiy-siyosiy va madaniy-ma'rifiy vazifalarni hal etishda ta'lim, ma'naviyatni tarbiyalash va rivojlantirish muommolariga alohida e'tibor berilayotganiga bag'ishlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ma'naviyat va ma'rifat, madaniyat, keng ko'lamlil o'zgarishlar, Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosati, jamiyat, intellektual, davr, mutafakkir, umumbashariy.

Аннотация. В данной статье молодежь, которая является будущим нашей страны, должна быть воспитана духовно, нравственно и физически, а также сделать ее активными участниками проводимых реформ. Особое внимание уделено проблемам воспитания и развития характера.

Ключевые слова: Духовность и просвещение, культура, масштабные изменения, государственная политика в отношении молодежи, общество, интеллектуал, эпоха, мыслитель, общечеловеческий.

The criteria that shape spirituality are a concept that affects the human mind, puts its World View, way of thinking in a certain direction, changes, society generalizes spiritual cultural and material foundations, traditions, values, heritage, lifestyle and views inherent in the nation.

In the history of our region, the criteria for raising spirituality have been enriched for centuries and formed the foundations of spiritual heritage. Within the criteria that elevate spirituality, material heritage has a special place of its own, and material heritage has for many years become an integral part of the life of every people, nation and a powerful factor that affects human perfection[1].

What kind of development of society, spiritual maturation of members of society was carried out on the basis of a continuous unity of cultural, educational ideological work based on certain ideas. It is on the basis of history itself that its criteria, the continuity of their system, are of great importance in raising the spiritual potential of young people. The criteria for raising morale can be weak, the goals set cannot be achieved.

The more effective the means of raising morale and their criteria are used, the more opportunities for increasing the spiritual potential of young people will continue to increase. Educational institutions, media, information resource centers, theater, cinema, art palaces and

many other institutions that operate directly in our current society, have a great influence on human education, in general, are of great importance in the formation of a spiritual worldview, constitute a system of spiritual boosters[2].

The issue of raising the spiritual potential of young people is inherent in every era and society, in which it is necessary to analyze in depth all the factors and criteria that shape and influence spirituality before the state and society, and to scientifically analyze how they act in this regard. The history of any people or nation, their activities in the spiritual education of young people cannot be imagined in some way from the history of this people, their own traditions, traditions, life values. In this regard, natural spiritual heritage, cultural property, collective historical monuments serve as the most important factor[3].

The great people, scientists, thinkers, politicians and warlords who have grown up on the land of Central Asia have been born and matured at this point in the rise to the historically highest stage of secular science, which has become an integral part of universal civilization and culture.

On this land, sacred to us, culture, art, literature have developed and become factors that greatly affect the upbringing of young people.

The history of mankind has established that no society has been able to imagine its prospects, spiritual maturity of young people, without developing cultural-spiritual opportunities, spiritual-moral values in the minds and hearts of people and without developing or improving them.

The use of factors and means that elevate spirituality serves to strengthen the foundations of any state and society.

A country in which the morale of members of the community, especially young people, is impoverished, cannot have its own future. Spiritual poverty, spiritual crisis, intellectual non-fiction of a person were extremely dangerous for the development of society even at all times.

History itself has repeatedly substantiated the fact that the problems of society in political, social life, the impoverishment of youth spirituality arise mainly as a result of spiritual weakening, neglect of the means of raising spirituality. Cultural and spiritual progress, spiritual maturation of young people have a great place in the life of all mankind and are also an important vital necessity for the independence and development path of an independent Uzbekistan as it has been.

The richer the criteria that shape spirituality, the greater the chances of raising spirituality and raising a younger generation that is spiritually competent will continue to grow.

One of the factors that shape spirituality is spiritual heritage. Spiritual heritage is a product of spiritual progress, it is a set of age-old values that are passed down from ancestors to generations, created by human intelligence, which has the property of leading the future generation towards noble progress. Spiritual heritage plays a huge role in influencing the consciousness, inner world, way of thinking, feelings of members of society, developing their enrichment, managing new ideological directions. Spiritual heritage has been of great importance as values that deeply affect the way people live. That is why the restoration of the immense, immaculate spiritual and cultural heritage, created by our ancestors for many centuries from the very first days of our independence, has become an extremely important task that has risen to the level of Public Policy.

Not a single society can imagine its prospects without spiritual opportunities, without developing and strengthening spiritual and moral values in the minds of people. It is important in the composition of traditions, folk oral creativity, science, literature, art and other spiritual heritage. During the years of independence, the attitude towards the components of spiritual heritage in these areas radically changed[4]. Spiritual heritage has its own special place in the system of means of exalting spirituality.

Culture, enlightenment and ideology, which are of great importance in the life of society, are also considered to be factors that elevate spirituality. The development of society, human spiritual maturation is carried out on the basis of a continuous unity of cultural educational, ideological work based on certain ideas. These factors of spiritual maturation cannot be distinguished from each other. If spiritual factors are weak, educational work cannot be established. Without enlightenment, spirituality is also absorbed into the human soul and cannot be the basis of its activity. The process of raising the spiritual potential of young people, the system of means of raising spirituality cannot be imagined without culture, enlightenment and ideology.

Culture is considered an important factor that greatly affects human perfection, the rise of society's life, it is the system of material and spiritual wealth that people create in the field of economic, social, political and spiritual life of society, produce to meet their own life needs[5].

A culture that has its place in the criteria for raising spirituality is divided into material and spiritual cultures, which are created in different periods and socio-economic conditions. Therefore, the criteria of culture that elevate spirituality cannot be the same in all peoples and historical times. The content, essence of its culture is also absorbed into the minds of people and becomes part of the spiritual world. Cultural progress is carried out at the expense of the positive aspects of material and spiritual wealth created in different periods, conditions, and serves as a factor that elevates spirituality.

Enlightenment also plays a special role in improving the spiritual life of society, raising the spiritual potential of young people. Enlightenment is the main condition for human spiritual maturation.

The absorption of certain knowledge, ideas, beliefs, faith, norms of morality and decency into the minds of people, the improvement of educational work are the main tasks facing the Enlightenment. The promotion of ideas, knowledge, norms of morality and decency, which positively affect the development of society and human perfection, is considered an educational activity, and such an action, which has a great influence on spiritual growth, has always been appreciated by our people. The correct Organization of educational activities has a huge impact on the mental and moral maturity of a person. Humanity has always assessed its educational activity as one of the most progressive directions in the spiritual life of society. The maturation of a person does not take place without enlightenment. Educational activities associated with certain goals the influence of Family, Community, Society raises the inner spiritual capabilities of a person to the level of spirituality, forms his moral, decency, knowledge, qualifications, faith, worldview, ideological views.

During the years of independence, great attention has been paid to the elevation of the Enlightenment. Today, raising education in Uzbekistan on the principles of high spirituality has become the most important task in this field[6].

Educational activities, which have a great influence on the rise of spirituality, have at all times had the task of influencing the will of the human mind, instilling ideas of goodness in the human soul and educating young people in the spirit of spiritual qualities.

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